

ST. ALOYSIUS' COLLEGE (AUTONOMOUS), JABALPUR

St. Aloysius' College (Autonomous)
Jabalpur Re-Accredited "A" grade by NAAC

2022-2023

RESEARCH PROJECT ON

IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON YOUTH

For

PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS OF

BACHELORS OF COMMERCE (HONOURS)

IN

ST. ALOYSIUS' COLLEGE (AUTONOMOUS), JABALPUR (MP)

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2022-2023

BACHELORS OF COMMERCE (HONOURS)

DECLARATION OF THE STUDENT

I..... do hereby declare that the project report on '.....'is based on my original research work carried out by me under the guidance of Dr. Surbhi Jain and Mr. Harbaksh Moolchandani for the partial fulfillment of requirements of B.Com (Honours) for the assessment year 2022-23. All data represented in this project is true and correct to the best of my knowledge and belief. This work has not been submitted for any other degree or exam anywhere else.

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BACHELORS OF COMMERCE (HONOURS) CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the research project entitled as 'Topic Name.....' which is being submitted herewith for the award of degree of B.Com Honours by Student Name..... is done under our supervision and guidance.

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CHAPTER 1

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Social media is most recent form of media and having many features and characteristics. It have many facilities on same channel like as communicating ,texting, images sharing , audio and video sharing , fast publishing, linking with all over world, direct connecting. It is also cheapest fast access to the world so it is very important for all age of peoples. Its use is increasing day by day with high rate in all over the world. Majority of youth is shifting speedily from electronic media like as television viewers and radio listeners to the social media among all age of group. Youth rate is very much to shifting into social media so its influences are much on youth. This craze of social media has led to a host of question regarding its impact on society, while it is agreed that the social media affects people's living styles and it is an ongoing process to identify the nature of these influence in every society and country specially on youth .this study also focused the influences of social media on youth and their life style, trends, educational and political awareness, physical activities, social life, their learning and so on. Andres Kaplan (2010) described in his study that social media is a set of internet based application that constructs on the ideological and technological foundation of wed and that permit the design and exchange of user generated content (Chukwuebuka, 2013). Merriam Webster encyclopedia Britannica Company defines: youth is the time of life when someone is young. Youth is the time when a young person has not yet become an adult. Youth is very important for future of any nation and country's progress and development. Now a day Social media is essential for youth in the field of education to learn new trends in education, to improve writing and communicating skills, cultural promoting, religious and political information gathering and sharing links, better living style, growth and development of society (Merriam Encyclopedia, 2001). The internet and Indian life project: social media internet has different impact in various aspects on Indian's life. And this project covers the different areas of life in which some areas are here demographics, government official and on line elections and policies, education, family, friends and community, health, news and events, internet evaluation, online activities and searches, Public policy, technology, media and use of media (Turow, 2011). Social media such as Facebook, Skype, Twitter, YouTube and MySpace may

have been freshly marketed as great leveler as gathering in which divides of races, classes, and ethnicity. Shrestha lucky (2013) described that social media is means of connections among people in which they create, share, and exchange information and ideas in virtual communities and networks (Shrestha lucky, 2013). Alison Doyle an Indian Psychologist: She define Social media as, it is various online technology tools that enable people to communicate easily and people use social media to share information , text, audio, video, images, podcasts, and other multimedia communication. Whereas Anthony J. Bradley (2009) he defines Social media is an inevitable for the vast majority of organizations worldwide. He says this predictability is not assurance of success. He says many organizations fail in social-media efforts because they do not deliver their products on the six core principles that set social media apart and bring about its unique value. And these Six Core Principles of are social media collaboration. Social media network site define social media as: it is an online location where people can interact with others about information, entertainment, news and which will be on their own choice and creation (Turow, 2011).

IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON YOUTH

Social media having various impacts on youth's life in both ends some time impacts are in the favor of youth's social life and sometimes theses impact are negative to its user. Social Media might be sometimes seemed like just a new set of cool tools for involving young people. Sometimes you may use it this way and that's ok there are some pretty cool new tools around but the emergence of social media potentially has a bigger impact than that. It impacts upon young people who are growing up in an age where media is not about broadcast content from the TV, but is about interactivity, multimedia and multi-tasking. And it impacts upon organizations who need to remain relevant to a new generation, and who find their own work and structures being changed by changing communication tools and patterns of communications (Anthony, 2009).

Social media impact on youth on both ends good and bad social media is one of most influences impacting source throughout the world including Pakistan people do have these influences of social media which has enhanced the exposure of the people and create more awareness among youth. Youth is highly involved in social media. BBC news research (2013) their research discuss that sixty seven percent Facebook users very common and well known social media

portal comprised of the youth and students so this compliment the fact the youth and student have more focus and relation such asocial media the negative use of social media occur when students involves themselves in unethical activities on social media portal, sharing of useless information, and posting such as images that are injurious national dignity and foreign relationship of country (Sekho, 2013). Tanya Byron points out in the Byron review that in part, young people are turning to digital connection because fears about traffic or 'stranger danger' have led to restrictions on how much young people are allowed to go out and socialize. Social media tools are woven into many young people's day-to-day lives. Young people are in conversation and communication with their peer groups using a wide variety of different media and media devices every day. 10 years ago, young people may have only been in touch with friends and peer-groups when hanging out at school, or meeting up in town. Now young people can be touch through instant messaging, social networks, online games and many other tools. Young people are growing up in a constantly connected society.

THE POSITIVE IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON YOUTH

- It enables them to maintain contact with their friends even if they are unable to see them as frequently as they would want.
- Social media keeps you up to date on important events happening across the world as well as in your local neighbourhood . Knowing everything with a single click of your finger is a huge advantage.
- The youngsters have the ideal environment in which to express oneself in ways they wouldn't be able to in public. This is something that improves young people's self-esteem and provides them a sense of social acceptance.

- It aids in the development of social skills, and the greatest part is that it may lead to the formation of numerous friendships. Young people like meeting new people and learning as much as they can about them. With the social media platform, all of this is feasible.
- Another intriguing Interacting with friends via social media is more pleasurable than speaking with them face to face, according to the influence of social media on teens.

NEGATIVE IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON YOUTH

- People of today's age place such a high value on social media that it has become a priority for them. They are addicted to social networking sites and neglect all of the important things in their lives, such as family, sports, and school.
- We can only see the virtual aspect of a person on social media sites. This implies that we can only see the aspect that they want us to see. Many people strive to project an image of themselves to others that they are not.
- Bullying is a regular occurrence among teens, and it is to some extent tolerated. Cyberbullying, on the other hand, has a major influence on the other peer since it may show on anyone's newsfeed and spread rapidly. Despair and suicidal thoughts are occasionally triggered by such situations.
- Some young people are more receptive to being persuaded than others. They may feel pressured to change their physical appearance in order to compete with the next person they encounter on social media.
- In social media, there is a lot of temptation. It may become an addiction for teenagers and cause them to get distracted.

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Social media networking of adolescents have a vital role to play in the advent and development of psychopathology. Online community social interactions are described as significant risk factors for mental health issues. Social media users are radically subjected to idealized self-shows. This poses a danger to youngsters' potential to appear superficial, but the awful effect may depend on a form of social media interaction.

A) POTENTIAL RISKS

Youth who actively keep up-to-date (i.e. self-directed use of social media) may additionally work to obtain advantageous feedback and to search for affirmation and for that reason, display better vanity, whereas young people who mainly view and respond to different posts(i.e. other-oriented use of social media) are introduced to these idealized displays, although they no longer get great reviews on their very own appearance, which may also lead to a fall in self-esteem. Cyber victimization, or the feeling of becoming a victim of cyber peer abuse, has frequently been reported as correlated with greater rates of self-harm and suicidal behaviour, as well as stress related issues. Other forms of peer encounters in social media, such as social isolation and online dispute can also put young people at risk.

B) DEPRESSION AND SELF-HARM IN ADOLESCENTS

Although entirely population-based research proposes a correlation between the use of social media and academic discomfort among teenagers, the influence of such technology can also differ between individuals and may even have a much lower risk of harm, such as it is indicated by a growing literature on experimental research. Girls prefer to invest more time on social media than boys, have more publicity about cyberbullying, and have a propensity to revel in more health implications that is consistent with the recent epidemiological findings indicate that depressive signs and symptoms, self-harm and suicidal thoughts have specifically increased in young girls.

C) BENEFITS OF USING SOCIAL MEDIA

There are a variety of possible advantages Connected with the use of social media, include opportunities for entertainment, discovery of personality and artistic expression. Among the most specifically stated advantages of social media use is social interaction, with 81% of teenagers claiming that social media helps them to feel at home. It can also provide resources for some young people to obtain online social support, especially to access to similar peer communities. Social media platform enables one to share or connect with others .It helps a person from one side of the earth to communicate and discuss things with a person in the other side of the earth. This is not just a form of entertainment; it is also effective. One should take advantage of this in order to achieve optimal outcome in education. Social media offers its users with a platform to get formulated. Internal effectiveness, which relates to individuals own capacity to recognize and engage in politics, and external effectiveness, or confidence in the accountability of political officials and organizations to citizens' demands. Students should use social media to promote social consciousness and compassion. social networking sites can allow young people to get in contact with peers. Social media sites encourage youngsters to live their life unaffected. In reality, several organisations have developed their own Facebook accounts for Sharing details with many other people. In addition, its effect on recruiting has indeed been increasing. Through creating profile pages on social media in particular LinkedIn, Facebook, and Twitter, together with the company's website, businesses are seeking suitable applicants for the positions available in their organization

1.3 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study is expedient to apply social media in right direction for youth and create cognizance among youth that proper use of social media become a solid tool to educate, inform and groomed the mentality level of youth social media refine their living style of public especially for youth it is also create an responsiveness that how it is effecting the social life the deteriorate social norm, society standards and ethics of society and create awareness among youth the aspect of social media.

1.4 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study seeks to find out the impacts of social media among the youth on behavior change. While the study recognizes that new interactive technologies have impacts on other age groups outside the youth bracket, and as such this study will limit itself only to the youths in India particularly Jabalpur (M.P) therefore, in order to collect responses from respondents, an online questionnaire was formulated and circulated among respondents based in Jabalpur, resulting in 50 responses .Therefore, owing to the lack of available resources, the scope of the study is limited in nature

CHAPTER 2

LITEATURE RIVIEW

A literature review is a survey of scholarly sources on a specific topic. It provides an overview of current knowledge, allowing you to identify relevant theories, methods, and gaps in the existing research.

1) Pouwels, J. L., Valkenburg, P. M., Beyens, I., van Driel, I. I., & Keijsers, L. (2021)

An important formation that must be maintained for adolescents are close friendships (Pouwels et al., 2021). Pouwels et al. (2021) indicated that close friendships are supportive, accessible and responsive. The rise of social media has changed the way adolescents maintain their close friendships, which which was formerly just face-to-face interactions (Pouwels et al., 2021). Pouwels et al. (2021) investigated the effects of social media use on friendship closeness. The study had 387 adolescents from different educational track, which included intermediate general secondary education, lower prevocational secondary education, and academic preparatory education (Pouwels et al., 2021). The adolescents reported six times per day for three weeks from their Instagram, WhatsApp, and Snapchat platforms (Pouwels et al., 2021). The findings of the study were that positive between-person associations of friendship closeness with general WhatsApp and Instagram use with close friends (Pouwels et al., 2021). Further, there was a small negative association at the within-person level of the general WhatsApp and Instagram with and without close friends (Pouwels et al., 2021). Finally, Pouwels et al. (2021) found that there was a large heterogeneity in the person-specific effect sizes of the within-person associations with Instagram, WhatsApp, and Snapchat use with friendship closeness. The researchers suggested the findings underlined importance of acknowledge person-specific effects in development and media effect theories.

2) Habibah, S., Karina, M. W., Wreksagung, H., Hastuti, H., & Kartini, K. (2021)

Sleep quality causes health problems and is often taken for granted (Habibah et al., 2021). Low sleep quality among adolescents could cause health problems and social media use has been correlated to the problem (Habibah et al., 2021). Habibah et al. (2021) conducted a study that identified the association between social media use and sleep quality among adolescents. The researchers recruited 188 adolescents. The findings of the study were that those adolescents with high social media use and a good quality of sleep were lower comparison to those with a low quality of sleep (Habibah et al., 2021). Habibah et al.(2021) found a significant association between the intensity of social media use and sleep quality among adolescents and that adolescents should reduce their social media use to improve their quality of sleep.

3) Wang, C., & Gu, X. (2019)

Adolescence are navigating a complex physical, cognitive, emotional, and social changes (Wang & Gu, 2017). Specifically, adolescents are developing identities through choices and decisions related to their personal development of which critical questions are being asked, such as “Am I someone who has the ability to succeed in school? (Wang & Gu, 2017 p. 2).” Wang and Gu (2017) conducted a study that investigated how recent high school graduates perceived online social capital, peer relationships, and academic identity during high school. The study had 1,286 Chinese high school graduate that participated in a survey. The results form the study were that there was an association between social capital and academic identity (Wang & Gu, 2017). Wang and Gu (2017) suggested that the implications of the study were that the results for research and practice were discussed.

4) Boer, M., van den Eijnden, Regina J. J. M., Boniel-Nissim, M., Wong, S., Inchley, J. C., Badura, P., . . . Stevens, G. W. J. M. (2020).

Social media has become part of daily life and adolescents are using these platforms at an increasing use (Boer et al., 2020). There is a specific percentage use of these platforms in adolescents' lives, Boer et al. (2020) found that the increase went from 25% to 45% between 2015 and 2018. The problematic use of these platforms has been revealed in two studies about European adolescents conducted in 2014 and 2015 showed the prevalence of addiction-like problematic SMU was 4.5% and 9.1% (Boer et al., 2020). Boer et al., (2020) examined three aspects; (1) the role of intense and problematic social media use (SMU) were independently associated with adolescent well-being; (2) the role of these associations varied by country-level prevalence of intense and problematic; and (3) the differences in the country-level prevalence of intense and problematic SMU were related to differences in mobile Internet access. The study had 154,981 participants from 29 countries that measured the time spent on social media, whereas problematic SMU was defined by symptoms of addiction to social media (Boer et al., 2020). In addition, the participants mental, school, social, and well-being were assessed (Boer et al., 2020). The results of the study was that the countries with a lower prevalence of intense SMU, intense users reported lower levels of life satisfaction and family support and more psychological complaints than non-intense users (Boer et al., 2020). Further, the countries with a higher prevalence of intense SMU, intense users reported higher levels of family support and life satisfaction than non-intense users, and similar levels of psychological complaints (Boer et al., 2020). Boer et al.(2020) reported that all countries, intense users reported more friend support than non-intense use and problematic users reported lower well-being on all domains than non-problematic users. Boer et al. (2020) observed differences in country-level prevalence rates of intense and problematic SMU could not be explained by mobile Internet access. The conclusion of the study, Boer et al. (2020) found that adolescents reporting problematic SMU are particularly at risk of lower well-being and in many countries, intense SMU may be a normative adolescent behavior that contributes positively to specific domains of their well-being.

5) Salk, R. H., Thoma, B. C., & Choukas-Bradley, S. (2020)

There has been discussion and debates about transgender identities and gender minorities identities in adolescences within the public and research/clinical communities (Salk et al., 2020). There is a growing body research that documents significant mental health disparities for transgender adolescents compared to cisgender adolescents (Salk et al., 20120). Social media is being used to recruit a diverse sample of U.S transgender and cisgender adolescent to conduct a large-scale study to study mental health. Salk et al. (2020) conducted a research study to document significant mental health disparities for transgender adolescents using social media to recruit participants. The study used Facebook and Instagram to post advertisements that targeted 14 to 18 years old adolescent to complete an online survey and 3,318 participants self-reported (Salk et al., 2020). The participants reported gender assigned at birth and current gender identity, mental health symptoms, and transgender-specific stressors and milestones (Salk et al., 2020). Researchers had 1,369 cisgender, 1,938 transgender that were 986 transgender male, 132 transgender female, 639 nonbinary assigned female at birth, 84 nonbinary assigned male at birth, 84 questioning gender identity assigned female at birth, 13 questioning gender identity assigned male at birth and 11 intersex youth as the first Gender Minority Youth Study in the U.S. for the study of adolescents recruited for a study on mental health disparities between transgender and cisgender youth. The results of the study were that social media is a feasible platform to use advertisements and a waiver of parental permission to recruit a large sample of adolescents, which included subsamples of gender minority youth (Salk et al., 2020). The researchers indicated that they remedied limitations in the existing literature by including appropriate measures of gender assigned birth, current gender identity, and detailed questions about transgender-specific stressors and transition

6) **Sampasa-Kanyinga, H., Goldfield, G. S., Kingsbury, M., Clayborne, Z., & Colman, I. (2020).**

Social media use is a sedentary behavior, and its use persists into adulthood (Sampasa-Kanyinga et al., 2019). Sampasa-Kanyinga et al. (2019) indicated that a study suggested that one-in-four students reported using social media for more than 2 hours every day. Specifically, Sampasa-Kanyinga et al. (2019) found that social media use is often blamed for having negatively impacted the way people communicate and there is a scarcity of research that examines the relationship between social media use and the parent-child relationship. Sampasa-Kanyinga et al.(2019) conducted a study that examined the association between social media use and parent-child relationship quality and tested whether this association is independent of total screen time. The participants were 9,732 students ages 11–20 years old obtained through a survey (Sampasa-Kanyinga et al., 2019) The parental-relationship combinations noted were mother-daughter, father-daughter, father-son, and mother-son (Sampasa-Kanyinga et al., 2019). The findings of the study were heavy use of social media of more than 2 hours was associated with greater odds of negative relationships between mother-daughter, father-daughter, and father-son but not mother-son. The findings were similar for total on screen time (Sampasa-Kanyinga et al., 2019). Sampasa-Kanyinga et al. (2019) revealed that there were no significant associations between regular use of social media of 2 hours or less and parent-child relationships. The researchers suggested that heavy use of social media is associated with negative parent-child relationships. Sampasa-Kanyinga et al.(2019) indicated that a longitudinal research study is necessary to disentangle the pathways between social media use and the parent-child relationship.

7) Ku, K. Y. L., Kong, Q., Song, Y., Deng, L., Kang, Y., & Hu, A. (2019).

The role of the news is to inform citizens and the role has become increasingly challenged in what is being called a post-truth age (Ku et al., 2021). The era of post-truth is described as ambiguous information, polarizing views, heuristic thinking and algorithmic bias (Ku et al., 2021). Social media platforms are increasing, adolescents consume their news through these platforms, and as their preferred source of news (Ku et al., 2021). Ku et al., (2021) investigated the relationships between social media news consumption, new media literacy, and critical thinking. The study had 1505 adolescent participants between the ages of 12 and 18 years old (Ku et al., 2021). The findings suggested that there was an internal news seeking motivation, a cautious perception towards social media personalized news algorithms, and a reported habit of new sources tracking each independently (Ku et al., 2021). Further, the predicted skills in thinking critically about real life news was reported (Ku et al.2021). Ku et al.(2021) indicated that the literature related to adolescents' use of social media news related to empirical research is behind, especially to the topic of adolescent are able to apply critical thinking to make sense of the real-life news.

8) Beeres, D. T., Andersson, F., Vossen, H. G. M., & Galanti, M. R. (2021)

There are variations of physical and psychological developmental patterns in each adolescent (Heena et al., 2021). Adolescents is a developmental period that begins at puberty and ends with with adulthood for persons aged 12 to 20 years old (Heena et al., 2021). These observable range of changes, as suggested by Heena et al. (2021) have become more peculiar during the digital era. An impacted area is are adolescents emotional intelligence which is persons' ability to identify emotions, both within self and others, distinguish between them, and use them to guide one's actions (Heena et al., 2021). Heena et al. (2021) conducted a study that investigated the relationship and gender differences between social media usages and emotional intelligence among adolescents. The study had 200 participants between the ages of 16 adn 18 years old (Heena et al., 2021). The findings of the study were that the majority of boys were high level social media users and girls were using social media at low levels (Heena et al., 2021). As to gender differences, the researchers found no significant differences observed across different domains and levels of emotional intelligence. Heena et al. (2021) indicated that social media usage was found to be significantly positively correlated with empathy dimension of emotional intelligence as well as overall emotional intelligence.

9) Tan, L., & Kim, B. (2019).

Young people are developing new ways of learning in informal spaces (Tan & Kim, 2019). However, how young people are using digital tools in the emerging culture of learning in informal spaces (Tan & Kim, 2019). Specifically, there are new ways of learning and using digital tools in informal spaces in Asian context (Tan & Kim, 2019). Tan and Kim (2019) used two case studies on social media as examples to understand how adolescents shape their learning online. The goal was to contribute to the evolving dialectics on social media and learning by examining how adolescents exhibit agency online (Tan & Kim, 2019). Tan and Kim (2019) suggested that Facebook offered high learner agency environments for adolescents to participate in self-initiated enterprise and allowed them to develop personal trajectories for learning (Tan & Kim, 2019). The researchers suggested that adolescents' pursuits of their passions on online spaces gave rise to intellectual friendships and development of personal pedagogies.

10) Weinstein, E., Kleiman, E. M., Franz, P. J., Joyce, V. W., Nash, C. C., Buonopane, R. J., & Nock, M. K. (2021)

In the U.S., 80% of adolescents between the ages of 13 to 18 use smartphones and social media and most use social media apps (Weinstein et al., 2021). Weinstein et al., (2021) found that scientists are divided about the relationship between social technologies and mental health. Specifically, the public is concerned about the potential associations between adolescent social media/smartphone use and risk for suicide (Weinstein et al., 2021). Weinstein et al.(2021) indicated that there have been no prior studies leveraging the qualitative methods to explore the experiences of adolescents currently at risk for suicide. Weinstein et al. (2021) conducted a study that examined social technology use from the perspectives of adolescent that were hospitalized for a recent suicide attempt or serve ideation. The researchers used in-depth interviews, coded transcripts using a thematic analysis to report the findings and had three research questions. The findings of the study were there were both positive and negative social technology uses and with most participants reporting a mix of positive and negative experiences (Weinstein et al., 2021). Specifically, the negative experiences included troubling regulating use, stress related to social media metrics, encounters with triggering content, hostility and meanings (Weinstein et al., 2021). The positive experiences included social connection, social support, affect-enhancing content, shared interests, and resources for mental health and coping (Weinstein et al., 2021). Weinstein et al. (2021) indicated that overall, the risks and benefits of social technologies use correspond with established offline risk and protective factors for suicidal thoughts and behavior. The researchers found that participants generally valued their break from social technologies during their hospitalization and viewed them as integral to social reentry and identified related concerns. Weinstein et al. (2021) suggested that future studies related to social technology and mental health should test well-being focused digital hygiene interventions for maximizing potential benefits and minimizing potential harms of social technologies for at-risk for adolescents.

11) Beeres, D. T., Andersson, F., Vossen, H. G. M., & Galanti, M. R. (2021)

The developmental context of adolescence is being affected by social media use related to their leisure time and maintaining social relationships (Beeres et al., 2021). Beeres et al. (2021) found that extensive social media use has been linked to various mental health outcome among adolescents, to include; reduced or enhanced self-esteem, reduction or expansion of social network, decrease in loneliness, and increase in anxiety and depressive symptoms. Beeres et al. (2021) conducted a study that assessed the longitudinal associations between the frequency of social media use and symptoms of mental ill-health among Swedish adolescents. The study had a sample of 3,501 adolescents in the 8th grade, ages 14–15, and were followed 2 consecutive years (Beeres et al, 2021). The elements that were measured were daily social media use as self-reported and mental health using a Strength and Difficulties Questionnaire (Beeres et al., 2021). The findings was that there is an association between adolescent social media us and mental health that is mostly driven by between-person differences and not by individual changes over time (Beeres et al., 2021). Specifically, the finding is that long time daily social media use may be an indicator of mental (ill)-health rather than a risk factor for future mental health problems (Beeres, et al, 2021).

12) Oksanen, A., Miller, B. L., Savolainen, I., Sirola, A., Demant, J., Kaakinen, M., & Zych, I. (2021)

The drugs that have been designated as illegal are a continuing public health and safety issues to the individual and society (Oksanen et al., 2021). The Internet has provided access to legal and illegal activities of which drug access is a part of these activities (Oksanen et al., 2021). Oksanen et al., (2021) conducted a study using theories related to criminology and using addiction research to analyze risk factors associated with buying drugs online. The researchers predicated that social bonds, low levels of self-control, and poor mental health are associated with buying drugs on the Internet. In addition, the researchers predicted that the purchase of drugs online would mediate the relationship between low self-control and regular drug use. Oksanen et al. (2021) had as participants that were ages 15 to 25 years old living in the United States (1, 212) and Spain (1,212). These participants were measured related to impulsivity, a sense of mastery, social belonging, psychological distress, excessive behaviors related drinking, gambling, and Internet use) were utilized to predict purchasing online (Oksanen et al., 2021). The findings of the study were that those buying drugs online was associated with lower self-control, higher psychological distress, and excessive gambling behavior, and excessive Internet use (Oksanen et al., 2021). Further, Oksanen et al.(2021) found that having online friends was not a risk factor, having strong social bonds with offline friends served as a protective factor, and buying drugs online mediated the relationship between low self-control, and regular use of drugs. Alas, Oksanen et al. (2021) indicated that more focus should be placed on mainstream social media services as sources of accessing drugs and online drug buyers have multiple self-control and mental health problems.

13) Abigail M. Findley, Jennifer L. de Rutte, Tracy A. Dennis-Tiwary (2022)

Social media use has increased drastically over the past two decades among youth and adolescents. Accordingly, research on the potential impact of social media use on health outcomes for these age groups has become an important area of enquiry. Early evidence suggests that, while social media may provide pro-social benefits for youth, negative experiences associated with social media use (e.g. high levels of social comparison and cyberbullying) may have negative mental (i.e. depression, anxiety, suicide) and physical (i.e. sleep disturbances, poor diet, weight gain) health consequences. Despite the importance of these research questions, few studies have examined individual differences in the impact of social media on health, or leveraged conceptual models to conceptualize risk and resilience factors. Here, we review the existing literature on youth social media use and health outcomes, and argue that the allostatic load model addresses gaps in the knowledge base by characterizing specific aspects of social media use relevant to health and by generating hypotheses concerning how social media use over time might influence health and well-being. We end by articulating future research directions, including examining causal mechanisms using longitudinal designs, studying these effects in minoritized groups, and working with key stakeholders (i.e., physicians, schoolteachers, counsellors, and nurses) to recognize common social-media-related health problems to identify points of prevention and intervention.

14 EMMANUEL UNEKWU OJIH ET AL (2015)

This study has been able to clearly demonstrate the effect of facebook usage on the academic performance of students of tertiary institutions in Kogi state. The observations drawn from empirical data revealed that students have embraced the use of facebook, and its academic application is on the increase, even though some of the students still see facebook as outright distraction, a good number of them have embedded it in their tools of learning like research, doing home work, linking up with mates and lecturers alike among others.

15 SUNITA MEHLA ET AL (2015)

The present study is an effort to explore the impact of social networking sites on student's attitude towards purchase, and suggest some points to overcome such problem. The study is based on the sample of 200 respondents from different colleges of Hisar district of Haryana state. The study employs factor analysis, where the 17 statements are reduced to six principal components through varimax rotation. The study shows that derived factors have been assigned appropriate names according to the variables that have been loaded on each factor.

16 CHIEMELA QUEEN ADAUGO ET AL (2015)

This study examined the Influence of the social media on the Nigeria Youths: Aba Residents Experience. In carrying out this study, the researcher employed survey method in which she used questionnaire to gather her data. The population of the study was Aba metropolis from which a sample of 400 was drawn. The researcher asked research questions and formulated research hypotheses to guide the study. Relevant literatures were reviewed for the study.

17INDRAJIT ROY CHOWDHURY AND BISWAJEET SAHA (2015)

An important Social networking Site like Facebook is becoming more popular among the young generation in Kolkata. However this SNS (Social Networking Site) has become a touchy part of the daily life of the youth's and they are used to access regularly for a prolong time periods to share their ideas, comments, thoughts or giving any statement regarding commendable and contemporary situation. Facebook has a lot of interesting features through which mid generations are attracted more and they are becoming more Facebook seeker and however it effects on their social life in a positive and negative way.

18HARPREET SINGH AND VIJAY LAXMI (2015)

The growth of social networking sites shows a significant change in the social and personal behaviour of Internet users. SNS has become an essential medium of communication and entertainment among the young adults. Though it has started to affect the daily activities of normal human beings, the popularity of SNS is not going to reduce in near future. Everything in this world can be used for a bad purpose as well as for good. It's us who can make the difference and utilize social networking sites wisely for the benefit of developing social bonds across the geographical borders. However, nefarious act of cyber criminals discussed in the article has to be brought to the fore and stringent measures should be taken to curb the menace. Cyber laws have to be fortified with advancement of rules as if violators cannot escape committing a crime, at the cost of societal values.

RESEARCH GAP

After going through the literature in India and outside, it helped in finding out the research gap which helped in framing the needs, scope, and objectives of the present study. So, we can find out that geographically most of the researches were conducted out of Jabalpur (M.P) and there was no specific study found that helped to find out the impact of social media on youth, so this study aims to find for the same.

CHAPTER 3

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology is a way of explaining how a researcher intends to carry out their research. It's a logical, systematic plan to resolve a research problem. A methodology details a researcher's approach to the research to ensure reliable, valid results that address their aims and objectives. It encompasses what data they're going to collect and where from, as well as how it's being collected and analyzed.

Research Methodology is a systematic framework used to solve the research problem by using the best and most feasible methods to conduct the research while aligning with the aim and objectives of your research.

The research methodology includes answering the what, why, and how of your research.

To put it in simpler words, you will explain about:

- **WHAT** –What is your research method, what tools you will use to collect and analyze the data, what would be your sample size, and so on?
- **WHY** –Why you are choosing what you have planned to choose?
- **HOW** – How do you intend to make use of the methods and tools to solve your research problem and carry out the research?

3.1 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To analyze the influence of social media on youth social life
2. To evaluate direction of youth to utilizing social media.
3. To evaluate the attitude of youth towards social media and measure the spending time on social media.

3.2 HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

1. It is likely to say that social media is creating awareness for youth in better leaving style.
2. It is likely to say that Social media is swift source of information and entertainment for youth's interest.
3. It is likely to say that Social media is great facilitator for youth in the field of education.
4. It is likely to say that youth is utilizing social media in positive way.

3.3 LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

- 1) The research was limited only to Jabalpur city.
- 2) The research was carried out in a shot span of time, where in the research could not widen the study.
- 3) The findings are based on the answers given by the employees, so any error or bias may affect the validity of the findings.

3.4 POPULATION OF THE STUDY

Population means the universe of study, in which the researcher proceeds his study and the population of this research project consists of the people living in Jabalpur including fellow students and parents as well. Drawing focus on impact of social media on youth with a special reference to Jabalpur.

3.5 SAMPLE SIZE

50 People were selected randomly who are fellow college students and parents in Jabalpur. Due to time and geographical area constraints, the questionnaire was filled with the help of google forms. Percentages are used in making comparisons between two or more series of data. So percentage analysis was done by comparing age and people's preference.

Sampling Method :-Simple random sampling method was used.

3.6 DATA TYPE

The process of data collection begins after a research problem has been defined and research design has been chalked out.

PRIMARY DATA: It is first hand data, which is collected by researcher itself. Primary data is collected by various approaches so as to get a precise, accurate, realistic and relevant data. The main tool is gathering primary data was investigation and observation. It was achieved by a direct approach and observation from the respondents of the questionnaire.

3.7 TOOLS FOR COLLECTING DATA

A questionnaire is a list of questions or items used to gather data from respondents about their attitudes, experiences, or opinions. Questionnaires can be used to collect quantitative and/or qualitative information. The data for research is collected through questionnaire which has been filled by fellow students and parents.

3.8 METHODS OF DATA ANALYSIS

1. For data collection questionnaire was prepared.
2. Data was used primary.
3. Collected data and frequency distributions were tabulated.
4. Further on percentage was taken out.
5. Graphs were used for analysis of data.

CHAPTER 4

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Data analysis is defined as a process of cleaning, transforming, and modeling data to discover useful information for business decision making. The purpose of Data Analysis is to extract useful information from data and taking the decision based upon the data analysis.

Data interpretation is the process of reviewing data through some predefined processes which will help assign some meaning to the data and arrive at a relevant conclusion. It involves taking the result of data analysis. Data analysis is the process of ordering, categorizing, manipulating, and summarizing data to obtain answers to research questions. It is usually the first step taken towards data interpretation.

It is evident that the interpretation of data is very important, and as such needs to be done properly. Therefore, researchers have identified some data interpretation methods to aid this process.

To discover the impact of social media on youth, the responses of 50 participants were taken by circulating the questionnaire and data collected was analysed. A good response rate was received in this study. The following sections represent the analysis of the responses to the questionnaire administered in this study.

TABLE 4.1 GENDER OF THE RESPONDENTS

GENDER	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
MALE	32	64%
FEMALE	18	36%

TOTAL	50	100%
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SOURCE: - Primary data collected through questionnaire

Figure 1 – Graphic representation of gender diversity of the respondents.

Source – Questionnaire of the study

Interpretation – From the results of questionnaire, out of 50 respondents, 18 (36%) were females and 32 (64%) were males. The results revealed that more than 50% of the respondents were male. Table 1 and figure 1 shows the gender distribution of the participants in the study.

TABLE 4.2 CLASSIFICATION ON THE BASIS OF AGE

AGE	RESPONDANTS	PERCENTAGE
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20-25	42	84%
25-30	4	8%
30-35	0	0%
35-40	0	0%
Above 40	4	8%
TOTAL	50	100%

SOURCE: - Primary data collected through questionnaire

Figure 2 – Graphical representation of age of the respondents

Source – Primary data collected through questionnaire

Interpretation

It is clearly visible from the table and the graph that the majority of the respondents were of the age 20 to 25 following them were the people from the age group 25 to 30. There were not many people from the age group of 35 to 40 and above 40 hence did not make a significant impact on the research.

TABLE 4.3 CLASSIFICATION ON THE BASIS OF AVERAGE TIME SPENT ON SOCIAL MEDIA

AVERAGE TIME SPENT	RESPONDANTS	PERCENTAGE
Less than 30 minutes	15	30%
1-2 Hours	21	42%
3-4 Hours	11	22%
More than 4 Hours	3	6%
TOTAL	50	100%

SOURCE: - Primary data collected through questionnaire

Figure 4.3 – Graphical representstion of average time spent on social media by the respondants

Source – Primary data collected through questionnaire

Interpretation

It is clearly visible from the above table 4.3 and Figure 4.3 that majority of the people (42%) use social media for an average time of 1-2 hours and only a few people (6%) spends more than 4 hours on social media.

TABLE 4.4 CLASSIFICATION ON THE BASIS OF MOST USED SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORM

SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORMS	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE

Instagram	24	48%
WhatsApp	16	32%
Snapchat	8	16%
Discord	2	4%
TOTAL	50	100%

SOURCE: - Primary data collected through questionnaire

Figure 4.4 – Graphical representation of the most used social media platform by the respondents.

Source – Primary data collected through questionnaire

Interpretation

It is clearly visible from the above table 4.4 and Figure 4.4 that majority of the people (48%) use Instagram the most and only a few people (4%) use Discrod the most.

TABLE 4.5 CLASSIFICATION ON BASIS OF WHEN DOES THE RESPONDENTS ACCESS SOCIAL MEDIA WEBSITES.

TIME	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
During free time	17	34%
At college	4	8%
During social occasion	5	10%
During meal time	8	16%
Any spare time	16	32%
TOTAL	50	100%

SOURCE: - Primary data collected through questionnaire

Figure 4.5 – Graphical representation of the most preferred time of the respondents to access social media.

Source – Primary data collected through questionnaire

Interpretation

It is clearly visible from the above table 4.5 and Figure 4.5 that majority of the people (34%) use social media during free time and only a few people (8%) use social media at college.

TABLE 4.6 CLASSIFICATION ON THE BASIS OF USAGE OF SOCIAL MEDIA FOR ONLINE LEARNING.

USAGE	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Very often	35	70%
Upto a large extent	10	20%
Upto a moderate extent	4	8%

Never	1	2%
TOTAL	50	100%

SOURCE: - Primary data collected through questionnaire

Figure 4.6 – Graphical representation of the usage of social media by respondents for the purpose of online learning.

Source – Primary data collected through questionnaire

Interpretation

It is clearly visible from the above table 4.6 and Figure 4.6 that majority of the people (70%) use social media very often for the purpose of online learning.

TABLE 4.7 CLASSIFICATION ON THE BASIS OF POSITIVE EFFECT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON SPELLING AND VOCABULARY.

RESPONSE	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Agree	16	32%
Disagree	11	22%
Upto some extent	23	46%
TOTAL	50	100%

SOURCE: - Primary data collected through questionnaire

Figure 4.7 – Graphical representation of the positive impact of social media by respondents for

Source – Primary data collected through questionnaire

Interpretation

It is clearly visible from the above table 4.7 and Figure 4.7 that majority of the people (46%) have responded that social media has a positive effect on spelling and vocabulary upto some extent.

TABLE 4.8 CLASSIFICATION ON THE BASIS OF BEST SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORM FOR EDUCATION.

PLATFORM	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
YouTube	26	52%
Pinterest	0	0%
LinkedIn	21	42%
Facebook	3	6%
TOTAL	50	100%

SOURCE: - Primary data collected through questionnaire

Figure 4.8 – Graphical representation of best social media platform for education chosen by the respondents.

Source – Primary data collected through questionnaire

Interpretation

It is clearly visible from the above table 4.8 and Figure 4.8 that majority of the people (52%) have responded that youtube is the best social media platform for education.

TABLE 4.9 CLASSIFICATION ON THE BASIS OF IS SOCIAL MEDIA A DISTRACTION TO STUDIES.

RESPONSE	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Agree	13	26%
Disagree	37	74%
TOTAL	50	100%

SOURCE: - Primary data collected through questionnaire

Figure 4.9 – Graphical representation of response towards if social media is a distraction to studies.

Source – Primary data collected through questionnaire

Interpretation

It is clearly visible from the above table 4.9 and Figure 4.9 that majority of the people (74%) have responded that social media is not a distraction to studies whereas the rest (26%) agree that social media is a distraction to studies.

TABLE 4.10 CLASSIFICATION ON THE BASIS OF USAGE OF SOCIAL MEDIA FOR ACADEMIC WORK.

RESPONSE	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Strongly agree	3	6%

Agree	7	14%
Neutral	11	22%
Disagree	29	58%
TOTAL	50	100%

SOURCE: - Primary data collected through questionnaire

Figure 4.10 – Graphical representation of usage of social media for academic work.

Source – Primary data collected through questionnaire

Interpretation

It is clearly visible from the above table 4.10 and Figure 4.10 that majority of the people (58%) disagree that they do not use social media for academic work, whereas a minority of people (14%) agree for the same.

TABLE 4.11 CLASSIFICATION ON THE BASIS OF INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON ACADEMICS.

RESPONSE	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Yes	20	40%
No	19	38%
Upto some extent	29	22%
TOTAL	50	100%

SOURCE: - Primary data collected through questionnaire

Figure 4.11 – Graphical representation of influence of social media on academics of people.

Source – Primary data collected through questionnaire

Interpretation

It is clearly visible from the above table 4.11 and Figure 4.11 that majority of the people (40%) agree that the use of social media influences your academic, whereas some people (38%) disagree for the same.

TABLE 4.12 CLASSIFICATION ON THE BASIS OF NUMBER OF EDUCATORS AND TEACHERS FOLLOWED ON SOCIAL MEDIA.

NUMBER OF EDUCATORS	RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE

0	5	10%
0-5	21	42%
5-10	17	34%
More than 10	7	14%
TOTAL	50	100%

SOURCE: - Primary data collected through questionnaire

Figure 4.12 – Graphical representation of number of educators and teachers followed on social media.

Source – Primary data collected through questionnaire

Interpretation

It is clearly visible from the above table 4.12 and Figure 4.12 that majority of the people (42%) follow 0-5 teachers or educators on social media, whereas on a minority of people (10%) do not follow any educators or teachers on social media.

CHAPTER 5

FINDINGS, SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION

5.1 FINDINGS

- The study found that 70% of the population uses social media very often for the purpose of online learning, which can clearly be marked as one of the benefits of using social media.
- The study found that the usage social media has had a positive effect on the spelling and vocabulary of the users upto some extent, which may prove to beneficial for the young and learning generation.
- The study found that YouTube is the most preferred social media platform for education, as it offers a vast variety of content to learn from and various content creators to choose from. LinkedIn being the second choice and a significantly professional platform.
- The study finds that Instagram is the most used social media platform by the population, as it offers an easy to use interface and a wide variety of content creators and individuals as well as business opportunities.
- The study found out that social media can be a distraction to study, which is a rather harmful downside for the youth using social media and prove to be a waste of crucial time for them.

5.2 SUGGESTIONS

To suggest that social media users should understand the intent of using social media and remain informed about the use of informational sites, as well as the data protection issues at stake with the use of applications. Teenagers must use their time productively on social media to improve social connectivity rather than squandering their valuable time on informal chats and posts in WhatsApp, Twitter, Facebook, and YouTube. To ensure the future of children, teachers and parents should look for what they are truly doing.

Teachers must introduce new techniques to allow students to get support from instructional platforms for their assessments and tutorials in order to inculcate the practice of using social media for academic purposes. That time is spent by young people using cell phones and browsing the Internet can be reduced by setting plans for their everyday lives. Parents or guardians must do this to protect their child from abuse of social media. Academic institutions must not regulate educational opportunities.

Influence and obsession on social media are much worse than the fascination with tobacco. Young people actually the most popular user of social media, encounter the issue of fear, anxiety, poor self-esteem, depression, and they are scared of being emotionally abused, criticized, or even ignored if they encounter people and improve their social connections such that they usually spend their time using smartphones and browsing through various public contact platforms.

5.3 CONCLUSION

This research deals with the impact of social media on youth, this study uncovered important information on the extent of impact of social media on youth. The questionnaire consists of 12 questions, the primary restriction is that the findings can only be applied to the 50 individuals that responded to the questionnaire.

Our young have been shown to have both beneficial and bad consequences from social networking. Individuals must select whether or not to use the sites in the future, or whether or not to use them at all. Parents should counsel and teach their children on current topics such as social media use, as well as the hazards of abusing or overusing it. Social media studies should be added to the education curriculum so that students understand the necessity of being cautious when using social media.

Conclusions and Suggestions for the Future During the previous two decades, new media has become a more important presence in the lives of teenagers, presenting both new challenges and new opportunities. A rising body of research is uncovering social media experiences that may have an influence on teens' mental health. However, because the digital media environment is rapidly evolving, further research is necessary. Much of the existing research is based on self-report measures of adolescent media use and is conducted at a single time point, making it difficult to make definitive conclusions regarding whether media use precedes and predicts mental health effects or vice versa. Future experimental and longitudinal research, especially those that use objective measurements like direct observation of teenagers' social media sites, are required. Furthermore, future research must consider the specific social media experiences and individual characteristics that may make certain adolescents particularly vulnerable to social media's positive or negative effects, rather than previous notions of "screen time" as a primary contributor to mental health.

QUESTIONNAIRE

1) Gender:

- Male
- Female

2) Age:

- 20-25
- 25-30
- 30-35
- 35-40
- 40 Above

3) Average time that you spend on social media

- Less than 30 minutes
- 1-2 hours
- 3-4 hours
- More than 4 hours

4) What social media do you use the most

- Instagram
- WhatsApp
- Snapchat
- Discord

5) When do you access social media websites

- During my free time
- While at college
- During social occasion

- During meal times
- Any spare time

6) How often do you use social media to participate in online learning

- Very often
- Upto a large extent
- Upto a moderate extent
- Never

7) Did social media have a positive effect on your spelling and vocabulary

- Agree
- Disagree
- Upto some extent

8) Which one of the following social media is best for education

- YouTube
- Pinterest
- LinkedIn
- Facebook

9) Is social media a distraction for my studies

- Agree
- Disagree
- Neutral

10) Do you use your social media account for Academic work

- Strongly agree
- Agree

- Neutral
- Disagree

11) Does using social media influence your academics

- Yes
- No
- Upto some extent

12) How many educators & teachers do you follow on social media

- 0
- 0-5
- 5-10
- More than 10

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